

Exploring Linguistic Paradigms in Language Applications to Augment Arabic Language Acquisition

Fawzi ALGHAZALI¹ & Mohammed ALZYOUDI²

¹ Mohamed Bin Zayed University for Humanities, Abu Dhabi, UAE
ORCID: 0000-0002-5559-1034

Email: Fawzi.alghazali@mbzuh.ac.ae

² Mohamed Bin Zayed University for Humanities, Abu Dhabi, UAE
ORCID: 0000-0002-0068-3396

Email: mohammed.alzyoudi@mbzuh.ac.ae

Article information

Submission	02/01/2025	Revision received	29/03/2025
Acceptance	13/04/2025	Publication date	24/04/2025

Keywords:

Linguistic inquiry
Arabits
Artificial Intelligence (AI)
Computational linguistics
Arabic as a foreign language

Abstract: This study presents an exhaustive analysis of the phonological, morphological, and pragmatic dimensions of an artificial intelligence (AI) application developed to facilitate the pedagogical dissemination of Arabic to non-native speakers. The research examines Arabits, a leading AI application created by the Alef Educational Institution, designed for Arabic language acquisition among non-native learners in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). The study evaluates the linguistic components embedded within Arabits and pedagogical framework, employing a descriptive-analytical methodology and focusing on operationalizing these components in practice. The findings of the survey yield significant insights. The application places a disproportionate emphasis on Arabic's phonological and orthographic aspects while marginalizing other fundamental linguistic elements. Also, language representation within the application may sometimes appear segmented, with opportunities for enhancing the connection to the natural flow of conversational interaction. Linguistic expressions and speech acts are occasionally introduced in isolation, which could benefit from a more explicit integration of social contexts and the pragmatic situations in which they are typically employed. Therefore, although Arabits possesses potential in Arabic language learning and teaching, its effectiveness depends on advancements in computational linguistics and the integration of more contextually grounded linguistic inputs.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Dilbilimsel sorgulama
Arabits
Yapay zekâ (YZ)
Hesaplamalı dilbilim
Yabancı dil olarak Arapça

Arapça Öğrenimini Artırmak için Dil Uygulamalarında Dilsel Paradigmaların Araştırılması

Bu çalışma, Arapçayı yabancı dil olarak öğretmek amacıyla geliştirilmiş olan bir yapay zekâ (YZ) destekli bir online uygulamanın fonolojik, morfolojik ve pragmatik boyutlarını kapsamlı bir şekilde analiz etmektedir. Araştırma, Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri'nde (BAE) Arapçayı yabancı dil olarak öğrenen bireyler için Arapça dil edinimini desteklemek amacıyla Alef Eğitim Kurumu tarafından geliştirilen öncü YZ uygulaması Arabits'i incelemektedir. Betimleyici-analitik bir yöntem benimsenerek gerçekleştirilen bu çalışmada, Arabits'in dilbilimsel bileşenleri ve pedagojik çerçevesi değerlendirilmekte; bu bileşenlerin uygulamada nasıl işlevselleştirildiği incelenmektedir. Araştırma bulguları önemli çıkarımlar sunmaktadır. Uygulama, Arapçanın fonolojik ve ortografik yönlerine orantısız bir vurgu yaparken, diğer temel dil unsurlarını görece ihmal etmektedir. Ayrıca, uygulamadaki dil sunumu yer yer parçalı bir yapıya sahip olup, doğal konuşma akışıyla bağlantının güçlendirilmesi adına fırsatlar barındırmaktadır. Dilsel ifadeler ve söz edimleri zaman zaman bağlamdan bağımsız şekilde sunulmakta; bu durum, sosyal bağlarla ve kullanımda karşılık buldukları pragmatik durumlarla daha açık bir biçimde bütünleştirilerek iyileştirilebilir. Dolayısıyla, Arabits uygulaması Arapça öğretimi ve öğrenimi açısından belirli bir potansiyel taşısa da etkili olması büyük ölçüde hesaplamalı dilbilimin gelişimine ve daha bağlamsal temelli dil girdilerinin entegrasyonuna bağlıdır.

To Cite This Article: Alghazali, F., & Alzyoudi, M. (2025). Exploring linguistic paradigms in language applications to augment Arabic language acquisition. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 19(1), 241–251. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15228458>

1. Introduction

Language acquisition is an intricate process involving the mastery of communicative competence. Due to its complex morphology, intricate grammatical systems, and many dialects, the Arabic language presents unique obstacles for learners. In recent years, the integration of technological advancements, particularly artificial Intelligence (AI), has received much interest due to its potential to improve language learning experiences. AI technologies provide various opportunities for developing intelligent systems that can analyze, process, and produce language. All these systems have great potential to promote more effective language acquisition. Natural language processing (NLP), machine learning algorithms, and chatbots have been used to improve aspects of language learning, such as vocabulary learning, pronunciation practice, and interactive learning settings (Gutiérrez, 2023; Vyas et al., 2020). Despite all such innovations and forward-looking opportunities, Saussure's hierarchical paradigms of linguistic inquiry still remain foundational in understanding language structure, offering critical insights for examining linguistic phenomena. The notions put forward by Saussure laid the groundwork for structural linguistics in the early 20th century, emphasizing the critical relationships between the signifier and the signified and the arbitrary nature of linguistic signs. His structuralist approach, which focused on syntagmatic and paradigmatic connections and emphasized the study of language as a system of interconnected pieces, provided insight into the composition and functioning of linguistic structures (Stawarska, 2020). From this standpoint, studies investigating how phonological, syntactic, and pragmatic dimensions in AI-driven language learning applications can offer valuable insights into using such tools and improving them effectively (Beccaluva et al., 2022; Sadikovna et al., 2024).

Studies investigating the effectiveness of AI tools for foreign language learning and teaching have been gaining currency in the last decade (Hwang et al., 2020; Yıldız, 2024), yet much of the previous research on this issue focuses on English language learning and teaching (e.g., Bahari & Li, 2024; Beccaluva et al., 2022; Zhai et al., 2024) due to its status as a global language. However, various AI applications are designed to aid and improve the learning and teaching of other foreign languages (Deng & Yu, 2021; Yuen & Schlote, 2024). Examining linguistic paradigms of AI applications for Arabic language learning remains relatively underexplored (Alharbi, 2024; Mohammed & Ja'ashan, 2025), and there is a pressing need for much research investigating the effectiveness of AI applications for teaching and learning other foreign languages (Wang et al., 2023). This study examines how these paradigms might be combined with AI technology to address Arabic language learners' unique difficulties. Considering the unique characteristics and complexity of the Arabic language, this study also investigates ways to advance methods that improve learning Arabic.

1.1. Research Objectives

This study examines the Arabic application in terms of how the Arabic language's phonological, morphological, and pragmatic dimensions are addressed and represented. Additionally, it explores how these linguistic elements can be effectively harnessed alongside AI technologies to mitigate the challenges encountered by non-native learners of the Arabic language.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Technology, Artificial Intelligence and Language Education

AI aims to improve the language learning experience by creating innovative educational environments focused on students. It plays a beneficial role at different educational stages

through various teaching technologies, such as personalized learning, hands-on activities, and teamwork-based tasks. It also includes educational tools like robots, games, and software designed to fit students' needs and interests. These tools help creatively address student challenges while fostering key 21st-century skills like problem-solving, critical thinking, and programming. Its central goal in language learning resides in improving learning through trial and error and creating life-like situations in which students can listen and practice the language as native speakers use it. It also introduces new ways to simulate language educational processes by saving students time and effort. Recent research highlights the positive impact of integrating AI-driven language instruction on the development of language skills. Yıldız (2024), in a study exploring the effects of ChatGPT integration in EFL speaking classes, reported a significant enhancement in the speaking self-efficacy of Turkish learners. The study also noted marked improvements in their conversational abilities, self-confidence, stress management, and enjoyment of the learning experience. Beyond fostering student autonomy and promoting independent language learning, integrating AI-driven applications aligns with the preferences of newer generations, who regard technology as an indispensable aspect of education and daily life.

In a separate study by Celik and Kara (2024) conducted in a private school in Iraq, Web 2.0 tools were employed via various websites to teach and learn English grammar. The findings revealed a notable increase in grammatical competence, intrinsic motivation, self-confidence, and a greater willingness to learn English. This improvement was partly attributed to educational online games and opportunities for students to analyze their common mistakes through group and pair activities. Additionally, Demirkol and Dişlen Dağgöl (2022) examined the perceptions of EFL instructors at several state universities in Turkey regarding the impact of synchronous online education combined with face-to-face teaching. The study underscored the need for more robust pre-service education and in-service training to effectively enable teachers to implement classroom interactional competence strategies.

2.2. Challenges of Learning Arabic as a Foreign Language

Foreign language (hereafter FL) acquisition is a multifaceted and intricate process marked by numerous challenges. It constitutes a highly complex cognitive endeavor that requires linguistic, sociolinguistic, and pragmatic competencies within a non-native linguistic system (Dörnyei, 2005). Mastery of an FL requires profound cognitive restructuring, creating new neural pathways, and modifying existing linguistic frameworks. Learners must navigate various obstacles, including phonetic and phonological differences, syntactic variations, and lexical peculiarities, which demand substantial cognitive exertion and heightened metalinguistic awareness (Gass & Selinker, 2008). Moreover, sociocultural factors, such as divergent cultural norms and communicative conventions, add layers of complexity, impeding learners' ability to fully grasp and employ the target language in authentic contexts (Larsen-Freeman & Cameron, 2008). Additionally, psychological barriers, such as anxiety, self-consciousness, and fear of making errors, further complicate the process, hindering learners' progression in FL acquisition. A thorough understanding of these challenges is thus essential for developing effective pedagogical strategies that foster linguistic proficiency in non-native environments (Brown, 2007).

Acquiring Arabic as a foreign language (AFL) presents distinct challenges for learners, primarily due to its intricate grammatical structures, rich morphological systems, and diverse phonological features. A key difficulty lies in the significant disparity between Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), which represents the formal, literary form of the language, and the

various colloquial dialects spoken across different regions, which complicates the simultaneous attainment of both communicative competence and literary proficiency (Al-Batal, 2018). Moreover, with its non-Latin alphabet and unique phonological system, the Arabic script introduces additional hurdles for non-native speakers (Ryding, 2014). Despite these complexities, recent advancements in AI technology have substantially facilitated learning Arabic. AI-driven tools, including language learning applications and chatbots, offer personalized learning experiences, adaptive feedback, and interactive practice opportunities, which are particularly advantageous in addressing the challenges posed by Arabic (AlAfnan, 2025). These technologies enable learners to engage with authentic language use, refine pronunciation through speech recognition features, and receive immediate corrective feedback, enhancing learning outcomes and rendering Arabic more accessible.

A study by Dajani et al. (2014) highlighted several factors contributing to the difficulties of non-native Arabic learners, including the characteristics of teachers, learners, and the language program itself. The study emphasized that teachers' preparation and the efficacy of their teaching methods, particularly their ability to design activities that engage and motivate students, play a pivotal role in making the learning process more enjoyable and effective (Dajani et al., 2014, p. 925). Regarding learners, the study found that the overall learning experience depends significantly on students' seriousness and their capacity to adapt to the new learning environment (p. 925). Additionally, the study revealed that students found their textbooks insufficiently supportive, both in terms of language learning and facilitating meaningful interactions with native speakers of the Arabic language (p. 925).

Abo El Seoud (2024) similarly underscored the persistent shortage of instructional materials tailored to Arabic language education, despite the proliferation of teaching Arabic as a foreign language (TAFL) program globally, including across the USA. This issue is further echoed by Busaidi (2015), who noted that while some Arabic language programs in Western countries and parts of the Arab world, such as Egypt, have developed resources to support Arabic language acquisition, the availability of adequate materials remains a significant concern for professionals in the field. In contrast to the abundance of textbooks, supplementary materials, and e-learning programs for languages such as English, Arabic language programs continue to experience a conspicuous lack of comparable resources. The literature review, therefore, identifies two key challenges in Arabic language learning. First, there is a persistent shortage of appropriate learning resources and teaching materials that may not align with learners' cognitive and linguistic proficiency levels. Second, the existing e-learning platforms and AI applications designed for Arabic language instruction often fail to present the language in a communicative and integrative manner, limiting their efficacy in fostering comprehensive language acquisition. There is a need for studies examining the potential of AI applications to enhance the acquisition of the Arabic language and reveal critical implications for Arabic language pedagogy.

2.3. The Phonological, Morphological, and Pragmatic Characteristics of the Arabic Language

Holes (2004) asserts that "Arabic is a Semitic language identified as belonging to the Afro-Asiatic language family" (p. 10). Even within the framework of Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), there exists a continuum of varieties, encompassing approximately thirty distinct dialects. MSA consists of twenty-eight consonant phonemes, three short and three long vowels. Holes (2002) further highlights that the Arabic phonemes contrast between emphatic (uvularized) and non-emphatic consonants, a feature distinctive to the language. Structurally,

MSA is primarily a verb-subject-object (VSO) language characterized by non-concatenative morphology. In contrast to English, MSA does not form words by simply concatenating morphemes sequentially. Instead, the morphological structure of words, including verbs and nouns, adheres to stringent rules that vary based on gender, number, and tense.

Watson (2002) provides further insights into the unique features of Arabic phonology and morphology, noting that “apart from its great intrinsic interest, the importance of the Arabic language for phonological and morphological theory lies in its rich root-and-pattern morphology and its large set of guttural consonants” (p. 280). She emphasizes that the diversity of dialects in Arabic significantly complicates acquisition for non-native speakers. For example, dialects like Cairene Arabic, spoken by approximately 12 million people in Cairo, Egypt, and San’ani Arabic, spoken by about 100,000 people in Sana’a, Yemen, exhibit marked differences in their use of short vowels, plural formations, and second and third-person plural pronouns. These variations can be extended even further. As Watson (2002) explains,

They also differ in their inventories of long vowels, with Cairene having five and San’ani three. The default vowel in San’ani is /a/, while in Cairene, it is /i/. San’ani tolerates initial consonant clusters, whereas Cairene does not (p. 280).

From a pragmatic perspective, language concerns structure and how it is used in specific contexts. The meaning of words is often context-dependent, as illustrated by the Arabic word “*mash?*”, which can convey different meanings depending on the situation. It may mean “OK” when signaling agreement, “Are you leaving?” when posed as a question with a rising tone, or even function as a threat when pronounced with stress on the first syllable. Another example is “*baseeta?*”, which may mean “simple” when referring to an easy solution or carry an ironic or interrogative connotation when delivered with a questioning intonation. “*Baseeta?*” can also imply a subtle threat when uttered with a falling tone in specific cultural contexts. Building on this argument, acquiring Arabic must transcend the mere identification of phonemes, morphemes, and orthographic forms. While these foundational elements are crucial in the initial stages of learning, mastery of Arabic must extend to understanding its pragmatic dimensions and how utterances function in real-world contexts. Using language appropriately across various social situations is essential for developing communicative competence, linguistic performance, and social interaction. A nuanced understanding of words’ connotations and pragmatic functions enhances their proper usage and facilitates accurate interpretation of a speaker’s intentions across diverse settings.

In the context of this study, the examination of Arabic’s phonological and morphological dimensions is intricately linked to an exploration of its pragmatics, mainly how words and expressions function within specific contexts. Distinct linguistic rules govern daily social interactions and communication, with diverse interpretations and intentions emerging during conversations. Moreover, grasping the pragmatics of Arabic enables non-native speakers to appreciate that communication often extends beyond verbal exchanges, encompassing non-verbal cues such as gestures and other forms of body language. This implies that promoting pragmatic competence in Arabic is essential for achieving full communicative proficiency.

3. Method

The study employed a descriptive and analytical methodology, primarily focusing on content analysis. This approach involved systematically exploring the features and structure of the Arabits application, including its design, organization, and content progression across various levels. Particular attention was given to aligning the material with cognitive and linguistic

learning strategies. The analysis highlighted the systematic progression of language acquisition, examining elements such as vocabulary presentation, phonological and orthographic representations, and grammatical features like verbs, adjectives, gender distinctions, and singular/plural forms.

Additionally, the study explored how the application scaffolds learning, transitioning from foundational skills, such as recognizing letters and their positional variations within words, to more advanced language tasks, including narrative construction and discussions of abstract concepts. A descriptive approach was also adopted to provide a comprehensive overview of each level, detailing topics, vocabulary, and the introduction of language skills. Furthermore, the analysis identified the systematic integration of specific linguistic elements, including dual nouns, gender distinctions, and sentence construction, into the curriculum. From the perspective of applied linguistics, the research examined the pragmatic and functional aspects of language learning. This included how the application equips learners to use Arabic in practical contexts, such as dining out, participating in interviews, or engaging in cultural discussions. The study also analyzed the phonological, morphological, and pragmatic dimensions of the language-learning process.

As Wilson (2011) argued, combining qualitative content analysis with descriptive evaluation enables the researcher to view the phenomenon from different angles. Herein, it helped to identify the strengths of Arabits application, such as its structured, user-friendly design, besides its primary limitation represented in the need for supplementary real-life practice to enhance theoretical learning. This methodology allowed for an evaluation of the educational framework and the overall effectiveness of Arabits as a tool for acquiring Arabic. The study systematically described the structured presentation of linguistic content, assessed its developmental suitability, and emphasized the interplay between theoretical understanding and practical application.

4. Findings

4.1. Arabits General Organizational Features

Arabits aims to teach the Modern Standard Arabic language in the four major skills (i.e., reading, writing, listening, speaking) quickly and easily through interactive practice opportunities and making the language learning process fun. The application's content and teaching method were developed by experienced educational professionals in coherence with the UAE Ministry of Education framework for non-native speakers, along with considering the difficulties learners often experience while learning the language. One significant remark is the inability to skip stages unless all previous levels are completed. It may frustrate advanced learners who wish to challenge themselves with more complex content. The other limitation is content presentation, which is sometimes monotonous and repetitive. The platform lacks multimedia elements, such as videos or interactive real-life scenarios, to demonstrate how native speakers use expressions in various social contexts.

4.2. A Critical Analysis of the Phonological, Morphological, and Pragmatic Features of Arabits

The Arabits application represents an innovative endeavor to harness the advancements in AI over recent years, aligning with the UAE's strategic commitment to integrating AI-driven education across various sectors. Alef Education (2024) stated,

With Arabits, you can learn and understand Arabic by completing reading and listening comprehension activities while tracking your progress. Our learning bits teach you vocabulary

and allow you to practice what you have learned. Lesson assessments let you check your knowledge. Our additional speaking and writing worksheets on the Alef Platform allow you to practice your conversational skills and become confident in Arabic.

Table 1.
Key strengths

Category	Descriptors
Vocabulary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The application organizes vocabulary into meaningful clusters, making it easier for novice learners to grasp specific expressions and concepts. • The bite-sized information chunks contribute to better comprehension and long-term retention of new vocabulary. • While vocabulary is initially presented in isolation, later levels introduce basic grammatical structures, such as demonstrative articles and gender-specific nouns. • The platform is regularly updated, incorporating new vocabulary clusters. However, the enhancements are often minimal to lexical additions rather than substantial interactive or multimedia content improvements.
Testing/Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each level concludes with a practice test designed to help users identify areas that require further focus before moving on to the next level. • After each level, users must pass a comprehensive evaluation test before advancing. This mechanism ensures that learners are adequately prepared to face increasingly complex linguistic challenges.
Pronunciation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each task includes subsequent drills to assess users' mastery of newly introduced letters, sounds, and words, providing immediate feedback on their progress.
Learning Approach & Accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It employs a student-focused methodology by utilizing "bits," miniature, easily digestible information units. This incremental approach facilitates deep understanding and long-term retention by enabling students to master one unit before advancing to the next. • The platform offers free access to all users and resources. However, premium users can skip levels, limiting flexibility for learners who may want to focus on more challenging tasks without completing all prior stages.

This platform is specifically designed for non-native Arabic speakers. It offers progress monitoring tools to foster confidence and provide a supportive learning environment, enabling learners to acquire reading proficiency in Arabic effectively. A thorough analysis of the platform reveals that it boasts numerous commendable features that distinguish it from other language-learning applications. The platform's key strengths are presented in Table 1. Despite these strengths, the platform also exhibits some limitations that could hinder the learning experience for non-native speakers. These organizational, phonological, morphological, and pragmatic features warrant further attention and improvement.

4.2.1. *Arabits Phonological Features*

At the phonological level, Arabits provides an accurate introduction to Arabic consonants, vowel sounds (molded), and foundational phonological elements such as "*sukoon*," "*tanween*," "*shadda*," solar and lunar "*laam*," and syllabic structures. The platform presents the phonetic anatomy of Arabic letters and shows how individual letters, such as those in words like (باب door) or (قطع cut), are articulated. However, while these phonological features are essential, they are unlikely to be mastered by fresh learners of Arabic solely through theoretical instruction. A potential improvement would be the inclusion of video demonstrations featuring native speakers pronouncing words in real-life conversations, accompanied by subtitles displaying the orthographic form of each word.

4.2.2. *Arabits Morphological Features*

The morphological features presented in Arabits include basic grammatical structures such as verb tenses (present, past, and future) and noun forms (the singular, the dual, and the plural). Although these are initial representations of Arabic morphology, they may pose challenges for learners unfamiliar with the morphological richness of Arabic. As Habash et al. (2016) note, Arabic words are morphologically rich, and undiacritized Arabic words are highly ambiguous. This is why morphology, specifically diacritization, is vital for Arabic Natural Language Processing applications. These traits can be improved by incorporating live videos or oral scripts for native speakers of Arabic using these expressions.

4.2.3. *Arabits Pragmatic Features*

Regarding pragmatics, Arabits offers limited contextual vocabulary, relying primarily on texts rather than real-life scenarios. Duffy (2008) explains that pragmatic analysis involves a set of linguistic and logical tools with which analysts develop systematic accounts of discursive political interactions. Pragmatic analysis focuses on how language is intended to be used in context rather than solely on the literal meaning of words. In this regard, Arabits could be enhanced by incorporating interactive videos or dialogues demonstrating how the same expression can have different connotations depending on the speaker's tone and attitude. This analysis shows that the Arabits platform lays a solid foundation for Arabic language acquisition, particularly in phonology and morphology. However, the platform would benefit from more dynamic and interactive elements, such as real-life conversations and multimedia content, to improve its appeal and effectiveness for non-native speakers. These enhancements would provide learners with a more immersive experience, helping them better understand the pragmatic aspects of Arabic and become more confident in using the language in diverse social contexts.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

While AI technologies have demonstrated considerable promise in enhancing language acquisition across various linguistic contexts, their application to Arabic remains relatively underexplored. By centering on Arabic, this study critically examines how the Arabits application addresses the phonological, morphological, and pragmatic dimensions of the Arabic language while also integrating these elements with AI technologies to facilitate language acquisition. The platform is notable for its structured developmental progression, advancing from basic phonological units to increasingly complex syntactic and pragmatic frameworks. Its intuitive user interface and incremental learning levels enable learners to progressively develop their linguistic abilities, from recognizing individual phonemes and letters to constructing coherent sentences and engaging in practical communication across diverse contexts. Despite these notable strengths, such as its clear structural organization, modular content delivery, and robust assessment features, the platform does exhibit certain limitations. One of the primary concerns is the inflexibility in navigating between levels, which restricts users' ability to tailor their learning path according to their proficiency. Additionally, the limited incorporation of multimedia resources, particularly videos and real-world conversational scenarios, detracts from creating a more immersive and engaging learning experience. While the platform does address morphological and pragmatic aspects, these components could benefit from more comprehensive and contextually grounded examples to enhance learners' understanding of the language within its authentic social and cultural milieu.

Based on this analysis, several recommendations emerge to augment the Arabits platform's efficacy further. First, it is imperative to integrate multimedia resources, such as video content and interactive simulations involving native speakers in real-life communicative situations. This would provide learners with authentic exposure to Arabic as it is used in various sociocultural contexts, reinforcing both phonological and pragmatic competencies. Additionally, while the subscription model is relatively affordable, accessibility may concern users in different regions. Therefore, offering greater flexibility in navigating between levels, according to individual proficiency, would accommodate a broader range of learning preferences and allow advanced learners to engage with content at a pace commensurate with their skill level. Furthermore, in the more advanced levels, there is a need to emphasize the morphological richness of Arabic, particularly in verb conjugation and noun pluralization. The pragmatic dimension should also be expanded to include more contextualized language usage, illustrating how meaning is shaped by variables such as tone, formality, and cultural context. Given the diversity in learners' educational backgrounds and learning styles, implementing AI-driven adaptive learning techniques would allow for personalized learning trajectories based on individual performance and challenges, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of the platform. Finally, introducing more interactive grammar exercises and conversational drills, complemented by real-time feedback, would facilitate learners' ability to internalize complex linguistic structures, enabling a smoother transition from theoretical understanding to practical application. These suggested enhancements would ensure that Arabits remains a robust platform for Arabic language instruction and expand its utility and appeal to a diverse global cohort of learners. There is a need for empirical studies that broaden the existing knowledge about AI-driven language learning approaches for languages with unique linguistic characteristics.

Ethical Issues

This study does not require ethical committee approval as it does not involve any human subjects in any part of the data collection process.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

References

- Abo El Seoud, D. (2024). *Challenges in teaching Arabic as a foreign language*. Cairo: The American University in Cairo Press.
- AlAfnan, M. A. (2025). Artificial Intelligence and language: Bridging Arabic and English with technology. *Journal of Ecobumanism*, 4(1), 240–256. <https://doi.org/10.62754/joe.v3i8.4961>
- Al-Batal, M. (2018). *Arabic as one language: Integrating dialect in the Arabic language curriculum*. Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press.
- Alduais, A., Qasem, F., Alfadda, H., Alfadda, N., and Alamri, L. (2022). Arabic validation of the pragmatic language skills inventory to assess pragmatic language development in preschoolers with and without pragmatic language impairment. *Children*, 9(6), 132–147. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children9060809>
- Alef Education (2024). Arabits. Retrieved from <https://www.alefeducation.com/products/arabits>
- Alharbi, M. S. (2024). Unveiling linguistic frontiers in the 21st century: A systematic literature review of the rise of big data's role in data-driven language learning in the Saudi

- Arabian context. *Arab World English Journal*, 15(4), 3–21. <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol15no4.1>
- Bahari, A., & Li, R. (2024) Revisiting technology-assisted language learning affordances for language components: A decade survey. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 32(10), 7301–7320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2024.2312910>
- Beccaluva, E. A., Catania, F., Arosio, F., & Garzotto, F. (2024) Predicting developmental language disorders using artificial Intelligence and a speech data analysis tool. *Human-Computer Interaction*, 39(1-2), 8–42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07370024.2023.2242837>
- Brown, H. D. (2007). *Principles of language learning and teaching*. USA: Pearson Education.
- Celik, B. & Kara, S. (2024). Reaping the fruits of technology-integrated grammar instruction in EFL classes at the tertiary level through web 2.0 tools. *Novias-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(1), 18–36. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10973103>
- Dajani, B., Mubaideen, S. & Omari, F. (2014). Difficulties of learning Arabic for non-native speakers. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 114, 919–926. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.808>
- Demirkol, T., & Dişlen Dağgöl, G. (2022). Exploring classroom interactional competence in synchronous online teaching platforms: Insights from EFL instructors. *Novias-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 16(2), 49–68.
- Deng X., Yu Z. (2022, June 22). A systematic review of machine-translation-assisted language learning for sustainable education. <https://scite.ai/reports/10.3390/su14137598>
- Dörnyei, Z. (2005). *The psychology of the language learner: Individual differences in second language acquisition*. New York: Routledge.
- Duffy, G. (2008). Pragmatic analysis. In A. Klotz, & D. Prakash (Eds.), *Qualitative methods in international relations: A pluralist guide* (pp. 168–186). London, UK: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Gass, S. M., & Selinker, L. (2008). *Second language acquisition: An introductory course*. New York: Routledge.
- Gutiérrez, L. (2023). Artificial intelligence in language education: Navigating the potential and challenges of chatbots and NLP. *Research Studies in English Language Teaching and Learning*, 1(3), 180–191. <https://doi.org/10.62583/rselt.v1i3.44>
- Habash, N., Shahrou, A., & Al-Khali, M. (2016). Exploiting Arabic diacritization for high quality automatic annotation. In N. Calzolari, K. Choukri, T. Declerck, S. Goggi, M. Grobelnik, B. Maegaard, J. Mariani, H. Mazo, A. Moreno, J. Odiijk, S. Piperidis (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'16)*, (pp. 4298–4304). Portorož, Slovenia. European Language Resources Association (ELRA).
- Holes, C. (2004). *Modern Arabic: Structures, functions, and varieties*. Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press.
- Hwang, G. J., Xie, H., Wah, B. W., & Gašević, D. (2020). Vision, challenges, roles and research issues of artificial Intelligence in education. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 1, 100001. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2020.100001>
- Larsen-Freeman, D., & Cameron, L. (2008). *Complex systems and applied linguistics*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Mohammed, G. M. S., & Ja'ashan, M. M. N. H. (2025). Exploring the effect of AI-driven contextual conversations on EFL grammar learning at university level in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Ecobumanism*, 3(8), 11909–11924. <https://doi.org/10.62754/joe.v3i8.5790>
- Ryding, K. C. (2014). *Arabic: A linguistic introduction*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139151016>

- Sadikovna, S. G., Mansurovna, V. F., Salixovna, R. D., Xikmatullayevna, I. I., & Bobajanov, B. (2024). The role of AI and web 2.0 tools in developing pragmatic competence of L2 English learners. *Spaat Reports*, 1(7). <https://doi.org/10.69848/sreports.v1i7.5098>
- Stawarska, B. (2020). *Saussure's linguistics, structuralism, and phenomenology: The course in general linguistics after a century*. Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan Cham.
- Vyas, Y., Chetty, G., & Boodoo, Z. (2020). Artificial intelligence in language learning: A systematic review. *IEEE Access*, 8, 100864–100881.
- Wang, T., Lund, B. D., Marengo, A., Pagano, A., Mannuru, N. R., Teel, Z. A., & Pange, J. (2023). Exploring the potential impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on international students in higher education: Generative AI, chatbots, analytics, and international student success. *Applied Sciences*, 13(11), 6716. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13116716>
- Watson, J. (2002). *The phonology and morphology of Arabic*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Yıldız, C. (2024). ChatGPT integration in EFL education: Path to improved speaking self-efficacy. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(2), 167–182. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13861137>
- Yuen, C. L., & Schlote, N. (2024). Learner experiences of mobile apps and artificial Intelligence to support additional language learning in education. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 52(4), 507–525. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00472395241238693>
- Zhai, C., Wibowo, S., & Li, L. D. (2024). Evaluating the AI dialogue System's intercultural, humorous, and empathetic dimensions in English language learning: A case study. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 7, 100262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100262>